

PLURIDENTITIES

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Problem statement

The integration of digital tools in the contemporary educational landscape has critically reshaped pedagogical practices and learning outcomes, particularly within the domain of language education related to multilingual practices. This transformation extends beyond the conventional classroom, expanding the scope of learning opportunities both within and beyond its walls. Technology-mediated learning environments have been demonstrated to enhance student autonomy and motivation by fostering interactive and self-directed learning experiences (Azad, 2023; Vasbieva & Saienko, 2018). This is especially crucial in linguistically diverse contexts, such as those in Spain, where different co-official and regional languages tied to identity and politics coexist (i.e., Aranese, Basque, Catalan, Galician, and Valencian), and technology can be strategically deployed to address a wide spectrum of learner needs ranging from linguistic diversity, learning challenges, and cognitive barriers, among others. Illustrative examples of the use of technology in education include the use of eTwinning for telecollaboration (Huertas-Abril et al., 2023, 2025), Flipgrid to improve oral expression (Huertas-Abril, 2021), and generative AI (GenAI) tools such as ChatGPT (Galindo-Domínguez et al., 2024; Van de Guchte et al., in press). By leveraging these tools, educators can cultivate an enriched linguistic environment that promotes engagement, collaboration, interaction skills, and critical thinking, thereby aligning with current educational paradigms that advocate for learner-centred approaches (Gravani & Hatzopoulos, 2021).

The pedagogical shift towards technology-enabled contexts must be underpinned by a nuanced understanding of the 21st-century learner, who often expects technology to be an integral component of their educational experience (Rathnasekara et al., 2025). These evolving paradigms acknowledge not only the multifaceted nature of students' linguistic competence but their diverse cultural and personal backgrounds that shape their identity. It is necessary then to align educational systems with learners' experiences, thereby enhancing engagement, motivation, and efficacy. This perspective is robustly supported by the Pluridentities multidimensional framework (Pluridentities, 2025), which posits that the development of plurilingual identities is central to current language education. Consequently, teacher-mediated technology strategies are essential to bridge the gap between traditional language instruction and the contemporary demands of the multilingual classroom. Yet, empirical studies exploring how teachers' technology mediation strategies directly influence students' development of plurilingual identity and motivation are still limited. This working paper investigates this teacher-student dynamic within technology-mediated multilingual classrooms.

The intersection of technology, language learning, and identity (Pluridentities, 2025) constitutes a complex and multifaceted phenomenon. Language is intrinsically linked to personal, social, and cultural identities, and the process of acquiring and learning a new language significantly influences the development of a student's linguistic attitudes and self-concept. As Dooly (2023) affirms, language functions as a critical marker of identity, and proficiency in a new language can enhance a student's self-perception and social integration. Consequently, this interaction is particularly salient in contexts like Spain, where several co-official languages, monolingual education and bilingual programmes coexist. In such settings, the influence of technology-mediated teacher practices in enhancing students' plurilingual identity and motivation becomes paramount.

Furthermore, the ways in which individuals engage with technology can significantly influence and reshape their linguistic identities. For many learners, digital platforms provide a vital space for self-expression and exploration of their linguistic repertoires, allowing them to navigate multiple languages and cultures within a digital landscape (Kamalova et al., 2020). Social media platforms afford individuals the opportunity to develop and curate their online personas through deliberate linguistic choices, thereby reflecting and constructing their multifaceted identities and agency (Minei et al., 2021). This process has the potential to empower learners to actively embrace their plurilingualism and foster a sense of belonging within a variety of linguistic and cultural communities, on local, regional, and global level.

Technology also facilitates the negotiation of identities in language learning contexts by providing access to authentic interaction. Engaging with peers from diverse linguistic, educational, socio-economic, religious, gender identity, and cultural backgrounds online can challenge preconceived stereotypes and biases, and promote cross-cultural understanding (De los Ríos, 2022). These interactions enrich the language learning experience by making it a genuinely social and communicative endeavour, moving beyond the mere learning of grammatical structures to include the development of intercultural communicative competence. Ultimately, by deploying technology to create these rich, interactive, and personalized linguistic environments, educators do more than just teach a language; they facilitate the formation of confident plurilingual identities, equipping students to thrive in an increasingly interconnected world.

In this context, and using a qualitative research design, this working paper aims to gather profound insights into Spanish students' and teachers' attitudes and practices towards language

use and language learning, and how the use of technology inside and outside the classroom can be linked to attitudes and identity development. Moreover, it intends to respond to the following research questions (RQs):

- Research question 1 (RQ1). What are the attitudes and practices of Spanish students between 14 and 18 years of age regarding the use of technology (inside and outside the classroom) for language-related activities, and how do these relate to their linguistic attitudes and identity development?
- Research question 2 (RQ2). What are the attitudes and practices of Spanish secondary-education teachers regarding the use of technology (inside and outside the classroom) for language-related activities, and how do these relate to students' linguistic attitudes and identity development?

Methodology

This working paper employs a qualitative research design to investigate the complex relationship between digital practices and plurilingual identity in secondary education in Spain. The research was designed to gather profound insights into teachers' and students' perspectives and attitudes towards different languages and how the usage of technology inside and outside the classroom can be linked to attitudes and identity development. By juxtaposing educator viewpoints with student self-perceptions, this working paper aims to provide a holistic understanding of how contemporary digital environments influence the formation and development of linguistic attitudes and identity in the Spanish educational context. Thematic analysis was conducted to understand the essence of the lived experiences from the two key stakeholder groups: secondary education teachers ($n = 16$) and students ($n = 28$). Data were collected through two distinct methods: individual semi-structured interviews with teachers and six focus group discussions with students.

Participant selection and recruitment

A purposive sampling strategy was used to recruit participants who could provide valuable, information-rich insights into the research phenomenon. Considering the nature of the research, two separate cohorts were recruited:

- Teachers. Secondary education teachers, who were teaching in secondary education in Spain were invited to participate. An email invitation was sent to high schools, resulting in a final sample of 16 participants from different locations in Spain. This sample represented a range of academic disciplines, contexts, and years of teaching experience.
- Students: Students who had participated in the quantitative phase of the Pluridentities project and shown interest in participating in the focus groups. From the pool of volunteers, 28 students were randomly selected, ensuring each of them studied at a different school to guarantee school diversity. These students were divided into six focus groups, ranging from 4 to 6 participants each.

Data collection

Data were collected between July and October 2025. Focus groups and interviews were conducted separately for the two groups to maintain the integrity of each perspective and to prevent power dynamics from influencing responses, as well as due to the different nature of the two procedures.

On the one hand, individual, semi-structured interviews were conducted by the researchers with the 16 secondary education teachers working in Spain. It should be noted that an interview protocol had been previously developed in the Pluridentities framework (Pluridentities, 2025) with open-ended questions focusing on their experiences regarding the use of technology to support students' linguistic diversity, attitudes and identity development. Interviews lasted approximately 60 minutes each, were audio-recorded, subsequently transcribed verbatim, and finally translated into English.

On the other hand, six focus-group discussions were arranged with the 28 student participants, also guided by the researchers. A specific discussion guide was used, prompting students to discuss their perspectives and attitudes towards different languages and how the usage of technology (both inside and outside the classroom) is linked to their attitudes and identity development. Each focus group session lasted approximately 30 minutes, was audio-recorded, transcribed verbatim, and finally translated into English.

This study was approved by the Ethics Committee of Vrije Universiteit Brussel (Ref. No. ECHW_593-WP4-5_Phase1) and by the Ethics Committee for Research Involving Humans (Comité Ético de Investigación con Humanos – CEIH) of the University of Córdoba (Ref. No. CEIH-25-28), and all participants provided informed consent prior to their involvement.

Data analysis

The data analysis followed a systematic, iterative process based on Braun and Clarke's (2006; 2021) thematic analysis, which allows for the identification, analysis, and reporting of patterns (themes) within the data. The process was conducted in six phases:

1. Familiarization with the data. The research team immersed themselves in the data by reading and re-reading all interview and focus group transcripts.
2. Generating initial codes. Significant features of the data were systematically coded using Atlas.ti 25.0.1. A preliminary coding framework was developed independently for the teacher interviews and student focus groups.
3. Searching for themes. The initial codes were collated and sorted into potential themes. At this stage, the analysis sought to identify convergent and divergent themes between the two datasets (teachers and students).
4. Reviewing themes. Potential themes were checked against the coded extracts and the entire dataset to ensure they formed a coherent pattern. This involved refining the

themes, collapsing some, and splitting others. The researchers compared their results and discussed the parts that were different to finalize the categories (i.e., groups of codes), codes, and their connections.

5. Defining and naming themes. The essence of each theme was clearly defined and named to capture its core meaning. A thematic network was developed to illustrate the relationship between themes.
6. Producing the working paper. The final analysis was woven into a coherent narrative, supported by vivid, compelling data extracts from both teachers and students.

Positionality

A reflexive approach was central to the research process, acknowledging that the researchers' unique perspectives and intersecting identities shaped their contributions. To ensure analytical integrity, the researchers explicitly accounted for their similarities and differences with participants, recognizing how their own experiences could influence the interpretation of the data. This reflexivity was operationalized through collaborative research dialogues to challenge assumptions and a deep, sustained immersion in the data, a practice of "living with the data" (Creswell & Creswell, 2017) essential for refined thematic development. Additionally, the researchers acknowledge that translation from Spanish to English is an interpretive act. To mitigate bias, they collaboratively translated and verified key data excerpts, ensuring semantic and contextual accuracy was preserved during analysis.

Findings

This section presents the key findings of the working paper, which are organized into three distinct areas of analysis. First, it outlines the teachers' perspectives towards languages and technology, summarizing their reported attitudes and experiences. Second, it details the students' perspectives, capturing their viewpoints on the role of digital tools in their language learning process. Finally, it reports on the specific digital tools used for language learning and teaching within and beyond the classroom.

Teachers' perspectives towards languages and technology

The thematic analysis conducted resulted in a network structured around several major themes. A central theme concerned the advantages of technology for language learning, while a contrasting theme identified was risks associated with technology. A further theme captured perspectives advocating for the prohibition of smartphone use in educational contexts. The analysis also identified themes related to students' informal/non-formal learning practices and teachers' perceived students' digital competence. Finally, the theme lack of resources was identified, pertaining to infrastructural and access constraints. This thematic network, shown in Figure 1 below, outlines the key topics discussed in the interviews in relation to technology in the learning environment in multilingual contexts.

Figure 1

Thematic network of teachers' perspectives towards languages and technology

Note. Own elaboration.

The thematic analysis of the advantages of technology revealed three predominant themes, distinguished by their frequency of occurrence. The most prominent was an increase in learner motivation, mentioned by 15 of the 16 participants, followed by the benefits of accessibility and adaptability of digital resources, defended by 13 of the 16 interviewees. These attributes were found to be particularly salient and effective within the specific context of language teaching and learning, explicit mention of 11 of the 16 teachers, where they directly support diverse and personalized pedagogical approaches. These advantages positively influence students' informal and non-formal language learning.

Regarding the risks associated with the use of technology identified a central, predominant theme: the lack of critical thinking among users, mentioned by 9 of the 16 interviewees. Apart from this, other four subordinate themes are recurrent, appearing in the interviews of 8 teachers. These include the prevalence of distractions, the challenges of infoxication and the abuse of technology, a discerned lack of teachers' digital competence, and the corresponding necessity for teachers' support to mediate these digital challenges effectively. This last topic is related to the perceived students' limited skills and digital competence. Moreover, teachers' risks and concerns regarding the use of technology are reflected in their perceptions regarding the prohibition of smartphones in class by educational institutions. Finally, the lack of resources is

mentioned by all the participants (teachers and students), as directly affects the use (or not) of technology in the classroom.

Students' perspectives towards languages and technology

Figure 2 presents the thematic network developed to clarify the complex interrelationships between three central themes concerning educational technology mentioned by students in their focus groups. The analysis visually maps the connections and tensions between the perceived advantages of technological integration, the concomitant risks associated with its use, and its specific application in out-of-classroom learning contexts.

Figure 2

Thematic network of students' perspectives towards languages and technology

Note. Own elaboration.

This network serves as an analytical framework to illustrate how the three dimensions are not isolated but intrinsically linked: the perceived advantages of technology contradict the risks associated with technology and vice versa, and use of technology outside the classroom is one of the advantages of technology.

The 6 focus groups mention a series of risks associated with technology: lack of reliability, need for limits, and risk of easing off (becoming complacent and not doing the work themselves). In contrast, a total of 5 out of 6 focus groups mention advantages related to the use of technology for language learning, highlighting three benefits: promptness, usefulness, and help in

pronunciation. In this line, it must be noted that half of the focus groups ($n = 3$) mention that they prefer learning language without technology, but assisted by teachers. For instance, in the focus group 4 a participant mentioned: “yo que soy mucho de utilizar papel... a mí me gusta mucho hacerlo de la manera tradicional, como siempre” (“I’m someone who uses a lot of paper... I really like doing it the traditional way, as always”).

Regarding the use of technology outside the classroom, 5 out of 6 focus groups state that they use technology to practice languages, while 3 out of 6 have their smartphones set to a language different from their main language, mostly English.

Digital tools used for language learning and teaching within and beyond the classroom

Table 1 below provides an overview of the digital tools employed for language learning and teaching within and beyond the classroom, as identified by teachers, students, and those recognized by both groups.

Table 1

Digital tools used for language learning and teaching within and beyond the classroom per group of participants

Teachers	Teachers + Students	Students
AI tools in general (56%), with explicit mention (beyond ChatGPT) to chatbots (6%), Gemini (6%), NotebookLM (6%), and Twee (6%)	ChatGPT (teachers: 31%, students: 100%)	Dictionaries and translation-assisted tools: Linguee (17%), Reverso (17%)
Graphic design and presentations: Canva (50%), Freepik (6%), Visio (6%)	Duolingo (teachers: 56%, students: 100%)	Twitch (33%)
Quizzes and assessment tools: Baamboozle (25%), Blooket (13%), Edpuzzle (6%), Google Forms (6%), Jeopardy (6%), Mentimeter (6%), Plickers (6%), Quizlet (13%), Quizziz (25%)	Interactive websites (teachers: 13%, students: 17%), including resources created with Genially (teachers: 31%, students: 17%) and Kahoot! (teachers: 63%, students: 50%)	
Podcasts (13%)	Social networks (teachers: 63%, students: 100%)	

Specific teaching tools: eXeLearning (6%), Minecraft Education (6%), Innovamat (6%), Microsoft Office (13%), Padlet (31%), Scratch (6%), Wordwall (6%)	Streaming of songs with lyrics (e.g., Spotify) (teachers: 25%, students: 67%)	
Virtual classrooms (25%), with explicit mention to specific tools including Educamos (6%), eTwinning (6%), Google Classroom (56%), Moodle (19%)	Translation tools (teachers: 50%, students: 100%), with special mention to WordReference (teachers: 6%, students: 83%)	
	VOD platforms (e.g., Netflix) (teachers: 44%, students: 100%), YouTube (teachers: 63%, students: 67%), and use of subtitles (teachers: 31%, students: 50%)	
	Video / Digital games (teachers: 50%, students: 33%)	

Note. Own elaboration.

Conclusions

These findings offer a comprehensive view of how Spanish secondary education students and teachers perceive and engage with technology in relation to language learning and linguistic identity development. In general, both groups expressed positive attitudes toward the integration of digital tools, although their practices and levels of engagement varied. The findings also directly address the two research questions. Regarding RQ1, students reported positive attitudes valuing technology's utility but demonstrated practices of passive consumption. For RQ2, teachers expressed strong belief in technology's potential but reported practices constrained by external challenges and a need for more training. These ideas are further developed below.

Teachers recognized the potential of technology to support multilingual education. They believed that digital tools could improve language teaching, as they break down classroom walls, making learning adaptive and more accessible for all at the same time they increase students' motivation. However, their actual practices did not always align with these beliefs, as while many felt confident using technology in their lessons, teachers expressed numerous challenges and concerns, pinpointing the lack of critical thinking, which can derive to AI-generated answers and plagiarism on the side of students'. Moreover, it is not always possible for them to use digital tools due to limited access to working devices, problems with Internet connection, or lack of funding to acquire functional devices and apps. The use of smartphones in class, which is forbidden by national regulations, is a controversial topic: although some participants consider that it can be a disruptive element, others clearly defend that students need to develop life skills to use them critically and ethically.

As for students, they also showed a clear appreciation for the role of technology considering its promptness and usefulness, and they specially highlighted that technology could help them pronounce new words in the target language. Despite these benefits, all participating students mention numerous risks associated with the use of technology, stating that they really appreciate having limits and privacy, as well as being guided and supported by their teachers. In this sense, it must be noted that students reported that tools such as social networks and streaming services helped them improve their skills and access multilingual resources. Their practices, however, revealed a tendency to favour passive consumption over active production in other languages because while many students watched content in languages other than their main language, fewer used those languages to communicate or interact online. This suggests that while

technology facilitates exposure to linguistic diversity, it does not necessarily translate into active multilingual/plurilingual engagement.

Challenging the myth of “digital natives” (Prensky, 2001), when analyzing the digital tools mentioned by both teachers and students, the former mentioned more resources than the latter. A consensus seems to exist between the two groups regarding the predominance of ChatGPT as a Generative AI tool. However, their awareness of other tools diverges significantly. The students referred solely to ChatGPT, while the teachers demonstrated a broader familiarity with a suite of specialized tools, including Gemini (employed as a ChatGPT alternative), NotebookLM (an AI-powered research assistant), and Twee (used for simplifying language lesson planning).

Social media platforms also play a key role due to their perceived potential for learning languages beyond the classroom by facilitating access to authentic target-language communities and content. Social media provides a domain for continuous, informal immersion, which fosters pragmatic competence and intercultural understanding. This autonomous engagement serves as a powerful complement to structured classroom instruction.

Taken together, these findings reveal a shared belief in the value of technology for language learning and identity development and highlight areas for progress. The interplay between student and teacher beliefs and practices mirrors the dynamic connections within the Pluridentities framework (Pluridentities, 2025), particularly the need for better alignment between technology, language policy, and the learning environment to fully leverage students’ linguistic capital. On their part, teachers are optimistic about the benefits of digital tools, but they require more resources, funding, and specific training to fully realize their potential in fostering plurilingualism.

However, a key limitation in this analysis is that the data reflect self-reported attitudes and practices; therefore, observational studies could further illuminate actual classroom dynamics and digital behaviours. Together with this, the implications of the findings of this working paper point to several next steps. Firstly, educational policies should encourage the active use of multiple languages in digital contexts, moving beyond passive exposure to promote meaningful communication and creative expression. Secondly, teacher training programs should focus on building confidence and competence in using technology to support multilingual practices and plurilingual students. Thirdly, curriculum designers should integrate digital tools in ways that reflect students’ preferences and habits, making language learning more engaging and relevant. Finally, schools must address issues of equity and access to ensure that all students can

benefit from technology-enhanced language education, bridging the socioeconomic gaps both inside and outside the classroom. By embracing these directions, Spanish secondary education can benefit more from exploit the power of technology to cultivate confident, motivated, and plurilingual learners prepared for a digitally connected world.

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